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JACOBS SCHOOL OF ENGINEERING

In-Situ Consolidated Automated Fiber Placement Carbon Fiber PAEK Composites

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Motivated Towards a Sustainable Composite Industry

Energy Expensive, Slow

& Non-Recyclable

High-Rates, Tough &

Sustainable End-of-Life

Outline

- In situ Consolidation AFP of Thermoplastic Composites (ICAT)
 - Overview of our system
 - Bond strength and fracture toughness in ICAT
 - Effect of tape staggering on interlaminar strength
 - Towards understanding bonding in ICAT: a materials science view
 - Conclusions

Laser-Assisted Automated Fiber Placement (L-AFP) In situ Consolidation AFP of Thermoplastic Composites (ICAT)

ICAT Processing-Structure-Properties

- Process variables: speed, temperature, compaction force
- Three factors per variable
- Short beam shear strength as response
- Nine samples for the partial factorial design of experiments
- Taguchi method analysis

<i>Sample</i>	<i>Speed (mm/s)</i>	<i>Processing Temp. (°C)</i>	<i>Compaction Force (N)</i>
#1	50	360	200
#2	50	400	300
#3	50	380	400
#4	100	360	300
#5	100	400	400
#6	100	380	200
#7	150	360	400
#8	150	400	200
#9	150	380	300

Results (1/2" tapes, no gaps)

Sample	Speed (mm/s)	Processing Temp. (°C)	Compaction Force (N)
#2	50	400	300
#7	150	360	400

Void Analysis

Crystallinity analysis

Sample	Speed (mm/s)	Processing Temp. (°C)	Compaction Force (N)
#2	50	400	300
#7	150	360	400

Post-annealed samples achieve a crystallinity of ~25% and SBS strength of 63 MPa.

Failure Modes: ICAT vs. Compression Molded

Repetitive Heating and Pressing

Fracture Toughness Coupons

Processing Parameters

- Speed: 100 mm/s, 200 mm/s
- Processing Temperature: 400 °C
- Compaction force: 400 N
- Heated Tool: 150 °C
- Material: CF/LM-PAEK Tape 12.35 x 0.13 mm

Fracture Toughness sample
fabrication

Solidification Kinetics

Crystallinity of

- 100 mm/s ICAT: 23%
- 200 mm/s ICAT: 9%

Tool temperature at 150 °C

Void Content and Shape

SBS coupons 100 mm/s

SBS coupons at 200 mm/s

ILSS, G_{IC} , and G_{IIC}

**SBS for post-processed samples:
VBO and CM is ~95 MPa**

G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} for Different Composites (DCB and ENF)

Strain Energy Release Rate in KJ.m^{-2}

Material	G_{Ic}	G_{IIc}
ICAT (0.2 m/s or ~500 IPM)	1.7	2.1
T300/914	0.2	0.5-0.6
AS4/3502	0.2	0.6
AS4/PEEK	1.3-1.7	1.2-1.8
AS4 Fabric/LY564	0.72	3.5
IM7/8552	0.2	1.1-1.7

Fractography of Mode I Coupons

100 mm/s

200 mm/s

Brittle fracture

Ductile + Brittle fracture

Ductile fracture

Fractography of Mode II Coupons

100 mm/s

Brittle fracture (hackles)

200 mm/s

Ductile fracture (matrix tearing and stretching)

Effects of Gap Defects (Staggering)

Staggering vs. SBS

Conclusions

- ICAT is a complex process: bonding strength with intimate contact, interdiffusion and solidification interaction needs to be studied and better understood in the context of composite's multi-scale mechanics.
- High-rate AFP resulting in low SBS ($<45\text{MPa}$) and high porosities ($>2\%$) may achieve damage resistance on par with thermosetting composites.

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